

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN NURSING STUDENTS' ETHICAL SENSITIVITY AND THEIR ATTITUDES TOWARD ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: A DESCRIPTIVE AND CORRELATIONAL STUDY

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Keywords

Artificial intelligence,

Ethics,

Moral sensitivity,

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Students

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship between nursing students' ethical sensitivity and their attitudes toward artificial intelligence (AI). The study population consisted of 2nd-, 3rd-, and 4th-year nursing students from a public university during the 2024-2025 academic year. The study sample consisted of 178 students selected by proportional stratified sampling based on class level. The data were collected using the "Personal Information Form," the "Modified Moral Sensitivity Questionnaire for Student Nurses (MMSQSN)," and the "General Attitudes towards Artificial Intelligence Scale (GAAIS)" between May 5 and May 26, 2025. Data were analyzed using descriptive, bivariate, and simple linear regression analyses. The students' mean total score on the MMSQSN was 148.05 ± 13.97 , their mean scores on the GAAIS were 44.08 ± 8.96 for positive attitudes and 22.52 ± 6.92 for negative attitudes. Students' MMSQSN scores significantly differed by receiving education on AI and gender; positive attitude towards AI scores differed by AI tool usage and views on AI's impact on nursing care; and negative attitude scores differed by receiving education on AI. A positive correlation was found between students' MMSQSN and positive attitudes toward AI, while a negative correlation was observed with their negative attitudes. The MMSQSN score significantly predicted the GAAIS score ($p < 0.05$). The nursing students' ethical sensitivity levels were neutral (moderate), while they generally exhibited a positive attitude toward AI. Ethical sensitivity was a significant predictor of attitudes toward AI. As the level of ethical sensitivity increased, students' positive attitudes toward artificial intelligence and their critical perspectives on its negative aspects also increased. Strengthening ethical sensitivity in nursing education may contribute to students developing a more conscious and balanced approach toward AI.

INTRODUCTION

The term artificial intelligence (AI) was first introduced nearly 70 years ago to describe the use of computers to simulate human reasoning. The integration of AI into the healthcare field began as a gradual process, initially marked by the development of a software program designed to guide physicians toward appropriate antimicrobial treatment¹. AI tools are used in various areas of healthcare, including clinical diagnosis, forecasting of illnesses, image interpretation, robot-assisted surgeries, and digital health applications². AI is being used in nursing education, practice, and management, and its use is expected to increase even further in the future^{2,3}. The embedding of AI into nursing practice has the potential to transform the way healthcare is delivered⁴. AI technologies and robots in nursing have a wide range of applications, from patient admission to home care³.

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Ethics is a set of moral principles or values that govern the behaviors of an individual or a profession. In nursing profession, ethics is defined as protecting the rights of the patient, avoiding harm, ensuring benefit, and deciding on what is right and good for the patient together with the patient. In nursing practice, frequent ethical dilemmas arise due to the intensive interaction with patients, highlighting the critical importance of the ethical decision-making process⁵. In nursing, the ability to make ethical decisions is dependent on the development of ethical sensitivity⁵⁻⁷. Moral sensitivity is the ability to identify moral aspects in real-life situations and to distinguish ethical problems^{2,6,7}. Moreover, moral sensitivity is a fundamental component of moral judgment capacity and also a precursor to ethical decision-making^{2,7}. Ethical sensitivity includes recognizing the ethical issue, demonstrating a contextual and intuitive understanding of the patient's vulnerable situation, and having an understanding of the ethical implications of decisions made on the patient's behalf⁷. Moral sensitivity, which can be developed through Professional education, is maintained by exhibiting behaviors following professional ethical standards⁶. Moral sensitivity affects nurses' ethical awareness^{2,8}.

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Today, nurses and nursing students encounter various ethical issues due to the impact of global changes in healthcare technology. Being a nurse requires assuming professional ethical responsibilities and actively participating in the resolution of ethical issues⁶. Moreover, nurses need to have an enhanced moral sensitivity to solve ethical problems². One of the goals of modern nursing education is to train nurses who have ethical responsibilities and to enhance their moral sensitivity^{6,9}. Nursing students' moral sensitivity enhances the quality of nursing care and effective management of ethical challenges¹⁰. Nurses and nursing students emphasize the need to strengthen ethics in nursing, especially as the use of AI continues to increase³. Considering the potential for wider use of AI technology in nursing education and practice, it is recommended that nursing students receive education on AI ethics. Universities have also recognized the importance of AI, incorporating AI-related courses into their curricula to enhance students' knowledge in this field. In this context, nursing educators should guide students in internalizing ethical values related to the application of AI². Nursing students' positive attitudes towards AI technology influence their acceptance and use of this technology^{1,3,11}. Nurses and nursing students have a positive attitude towards AI¹². Nurses exhibit a positive attitude towards the integration of AI technology into care practices, yet they remain cautious and hesitant¹³. Although there is a widespread positive perspective that AI will facilitate human tasks in various areas, concerns also exist that it may cause ethical issues, particularly in the field of healthcare^{2,3,13}. Therefore, developing ethical awareness and moral sensitivity is of great importance in reducing the likelihood of such ethical issues arising².

It is believed that investigating the relationship between nursing students' ethical sensitivity and their attitudes toward AI could contribute to addressing ethical issues related to AI. This study was conducted to assess nursing students' level of ethical sensitivity and their attitudes toward AI and to determine the relationship between these two variables. In line with the main aim of the study, the following research questions were addressed:

1. What is the level of ethical sensitivity among nursing students?
2. What is the level of attitudes toward AI among nursing students?
3. Do nursing students' ethical sensitivity and attitudes toward AI differ significantly according to their characteristics?

4. What is the relationship between ethical sensitivity and attitudes toward AI among nursing students?

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Design

A descriptive and correlational design was used. This design was preferred as it allowed for the examination of the current levels of ethical sensitivity and attitudes toward artificial intelligence among nursing students without manipulating any variables, and for identifying a possible relationship between these two constructs.

Participants

The study population consisted of 2nd-, 3rd-, and 4th-year nursing students (N = 252) enrolled in the Faculty of Health Sciences, Department of Nursing, at a public university in southern Turkey during the spring semester of the 2024-2025 academic year. There were 52 students in the 2nd year, 77 in the 3rd year, and 123 in the 4th year. Since the study aimed to assess levels of ethical sensitivity, first-year students who had not yet completed their clinical practice were not included in the study. The department curriculum includes no AI-related courses, but offers an elective on ethics. The study sample consisted of students who met the inclusion criteria: (a) being a 2nd, 3rd, or 4th year student in the nursing department, (b) having completed at least one clinical practice period, (c) being willing to participate, and (d) completing the data collection forms. The exclusion criteria included: (a) being temporarily not in active enrollment status during the data collection period, (b) providing incomplete data collection forms, and (c) requesting to withdraw from the study.

The sample size was calculated using the known population sampling formula ($n = (N \times t^2 \times p \times q) / (d^2 \times (N-1) + t^2 \times p \times q)$). For this study, with a known population size of 252, the minimum required sample size was calculated as 153, based on a 95% confidence level, a 5% margin of error, and an expected response distribution of 50%. Students were sampled using a proportionate stratified sampling method based on their year of study. According to the proportional stratification by study year, this corresponded to at least 32 students from the 2nd year, 47 from the 3rd year, and 74 from the 4th year. To prevent potential data loss, 200 students were invited. Of these, 9 students declined participation, 5 were identified as outliers, and 8 were excluded due to incomplete data. The study was completed with 178 students (2nd year: 41, 3rd year: 59, and

4th year: 78). The obtained sample represents 70.6% of the study population.

Data Collection Tools

Data were collected using the “Personal Information Form,” the “Modified Moral Sensitivity Questionnaire for Student Nurses (MMSQSN),” and the “General Attitudes towards Artificial Intelligence Scale (GAAIS).”

Personal Information Form, prepared by the researcher based on the literature^{5,13}, consists of questions evaluating students’ age, gender, study year, their status of receiving education on ethics and AI applications, their status of using AI in daily life and educational processes, and their opinions on how AI will affect the nursing profession.

The Modified Moral Sensitivity Questionnaire for Student Nurses (MMSQSN) was developed by Comrie (2012)¹⁴. The Turkish validity and reliability study was conducted by Yılmaz Şahin et al. (2015)⁹. The scale is a 7-point Likert-type scale that includes 30 items. The scale has six subdimensions: “Interpersonal orientation”, “Modified autonomy”, “Beneficence”, “Creating ethical meaning”, “Experiencing the ethical dilemma”, and “Getting expert opinion”. The scale score average is obtained by dividing the total scale score by the number of items. The items in the scale are rated on a scale from 1 to 7 (strongly disagree-strongly agree). Items 8, 24, and 29 are reverse-scored. The total scale score ranges between 30 and 210. A higher score indicates greater ethical sensitivity. Scale score means are classified as: very important (7.0–5.9), important (5.8–5.0), neutral (4.9–3.1), and unimportant (<3.1). In the study by Yılmaz Şahin et al. (2015)⁹, the Cronbach’s alpha was 0.73. In this study, the Cronbach’s alpha was found to be 0.72.

The General Attitudes towards Artificial Intelligence Scale (GAAIS) was developed by Schepman and Rodway (2020)¹⁵ to measure general attitudes toward AI of individuals. The Turkish adaptation of the scale was conducted by Kaya et al. (2024)¹⁶. The scale consists of 20 items, including 12 items in the *Positive Attitudes toward AI* subscale and 8 items in the *Negative Attitudes toward AI* subscale. The items are rated on a five-point Likert-type scale (1= Strongly Disagree to 5= Strongly Agree). The *Positive Attitudes toward AI* score is obtained by summing items 1 to 12. The *Negative Attitudes toward AI* score is calculated by reverse-scoring items 13 to 20 and then summing them. The possible score range is 12-60 for

the *Positive Attitudes* subscale and 8-40 for the *Negative Attitudes* subscale. Cronbach’s alpha values in the original version were 0.88 for the positive subscale and 0.83 for the negative subscale¹⁵. In this study, the Cronbach’s alpha was 0.89 for the *Positive Attitudes* subscale and 0.87 for the *Negative Attitudes* subscale.

Data collection

Data were collected between May 5 and May 26, 2025, by the researcher through face-to-face questionnaires conducted in a classroom setting. The study’s purpose and procedures were explained to the students before data collection, emphasizing voluntary participation. The data collection forms were completed individually and anonymously by the participants. Questionnaires were coded anonymously. Completion of the questionnaire took approximately 10-15 minutes.

Data Analyses

The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0 was used for data analysis. The dataset was screened for missing data and outliers. Eight cases with missing data were excluded from the analysis. Outliers were identified based on z-scores. Values with z-scores beyond the ± 3 threshold were considered outliers¹⁷. Z-scores were calculated for the MMSQSN and GAAIS scales’ total scores, and five outliers were detected (four in the GAAIS subscales and one in the MMSQSN). Data from five participants were excluded from the analysis. All statistical analyses were conducted on the remaining dataset, which consisted of 178 participants. The skewness and kurtosis values were used to check the normality. Accordingly, the results were between -1.5 and +1.5, signifying that the data were normally distributed¹⁷. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. To compare the scale mean scores between groups, the Independent Samples t-test and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used. The Tukey test was used as a post hoc analysis to determine which specific groups differed. Pearson correlation was conducted to examine the relationships between variables. A simple linear regression analysis was conducted to assess the effect of MMSQSN score on GAAIS score. $p < 0.05$ was considered significant.

Ethical Considerations

The study was carried out following Helsinki Declaration principles. Ethical approval was obtained from the Non-Interventional Clinical Research Ethics Committee of Hatay

Table 1. Comparison of MMSQSN and GAAIS Scores According to Selected Characteristics of the Students ($n=178$)

Characteristics	n	%	MMSQSN $\bar{X}\pm SS$	GAAIS	
				Positive Attitudes $\bar{X}\pm SS$	Negative Attitudes $\bar{X}\pm SS$
Age (years)= 21.49 ± 1.78 (min–max: 18-36)					
Sex					
Female	119	66.9	4.87±.43	44.12±7.80	22.62±6.17
Male	59	33.1	5.06±.49	44.00±11.00	22.33±8.27
Test			t=-2.570	t=0.079	t=0.232
P			p=0.011	p=0.937	p=0.798
Stud year					
2nd year,	41	23.0	4.96±.45	3.53±.64	2.79±.81
3rd year	59	33.1	4.95±.39	3.79±.80	2.87±.87
4th year	78	43.9	4.89±.51	3.65±.74	2.78±.88
Test			F=0.423	F= 1.589	F=0.236
p			p=0.656	p=0.207	p=0.790
Receiving education on ethics					
Yes	102	57.3	4.95±0.45	3.66±0.75	2.78±0.88
No	76	42.7	4.90±0.48	3.68±0.74	2.85±0.84
Test			t=0.768	t=-0.180	t=-0.534
p			p=0.443	p=0.857	p=0.594
Receiving education on AI					
Yes	43	24.2	5.07±0.53	3.56±0.48	2.51±0.78
No	135	75.8	4.89±0.43	3.70±0.81	2.91±0.87
Test			t=2.037	t=-1.421	t=-2.669
p			p=0.046	p=0.158	p=0.008
Use of AI tools in daily life					
Yes	142	79.8	4.93±0.48	3.72±0.73	2.80±0.85
No	36	20.2	4.94±0.37	3.46±0.77	2.87±0.92
Test			t=-0.159	t=1.846	t=-0.457
p			p=0.874	p=0.067	p=0.648
Use of AI tools in their education					
Yes	100	56.2	4.90±0.49	3.81±0.74	2.85±0.84
No	78	43.8	4.97±0.42	3.49±0.72	2.76±0.89
Test			t=-1.082	t=2.811	t=0.636
p			p=0.281	p=0.006	p=0.526
Opinion on the impact of AI on nursing care					
Yes ^a	97	54.5	4.95±0.47	3.79±0.76	2.77±0.87
No ^b	11	6.2	4.95±0.46	3.47±0.74	2.62±0.80
Partly ^c	51	28.6	4.86±0.45	3.38±0.62	2.90±0.76
No opinion ^d	19	10.7	4.99±0.48	3.93±0.75	2.88±1.11
Test			F=0.572	F=4.659	F=0.491
p			p=0.634	p=0.004	p=0.689
Difference				(a>c; c<d)	

MMSQSN: Modified Moral Sensitivity Questionnaire for Student Nurses; GAAIS: The General Attitudes towards Artificial Intelligence Scale; AI: Artificial Intelligence

Mustafa Kemal University (Date: 30.04.2025, Number: 06, Decision number: 39). Institutional permission was obtained from the faculty dean’s office. Informed consent was obtained from the students. The study was conducted voluntarily, with data collected anonymously. Permission to use the Turkish adaptations of the scales was obtained via e-mail from the researchers who conducted the adaptations.

RESULTS

The study was conducted with 178 nursing students. The mean age of the students was 21.49 ± 1.78 (min-max: 18-36), and 66.9% were female. Of the students, 23% were in the 2nd year, 33.1% in the 3rd year, and 43.8% in the 4th year. Additionally, 57.3% of the students reported having received

education related to ethics, while 75.8% reported no prior education related to AI. It was determined that 79.8% of the students use AI tools in their daily lives, and 56.2% benefit from these tools in their education. Of the students, 54% thought that AI had an impact on nursing care (Table 1).

The students’ mean total score on the MMSQSN was 148.05 ± 13.97 (Range: 114-188). When converted to an item-based mean, their mean total score was 4.93 ± 0.46 (Range: 3.80-6.27). This average indicates that students' ethical sensitivity falls within the “neutral” range of 3.1-4.9. The students' mean positive attitude score on the GAAIS was 44.08 ± 8.96 (Range: 14-60), while the mean negative attitude score was 22.52 ± 6.92 (Range: 8-40) (Table 2).

Table 2. Students’ Mean Scores on the MMSQSN and GAAIS ($n=178$)

Scales	Possible Score Range	Observed Score Range	$\bar{X} \pm SS$
MMSQSN	30-210	114-188	148.05 ± 13.97
Interpersonal orientation	1-7	3.75-7.00	5.78 ± 0.69
Modified autonomy	1-7	2.80-6.80	4.86 ± 0.72
Beneficence	1-7	2.63-6.88	4.60 ± 0.77
Creating ethical meaning	1-7	2.67-6.50	4.91 ± 0.68
Experiencing the ethical dilemma	1-7	1.33-7.00	3.96 ± 1.08
Getting expert opinion	1-7	2.33-7.00	5.07 ± 0.85
Total	1-7	3.80-6.27	4.93 ± 0.46
GAAIS			
Positive Attitudes toward AI	12-60	14-60	44.08 ± 8.96
Negative Attitudes toward AI	8-40	8-40	22.52 ± 6.92

MMSQSN: Modified Moral Sensitivity Questionnaire for Student Nurses; GAAIS: The General Attitudes towards Artificial Intelligence Scale; AI: Artificial Intelligence

A significant difference was found in the MMSQSN mean scores based on students’ receiving education on AI status ($t=2.037, p=0.046$) and gender ($t=-2.570, p=0.011$). Male students had a higher ethical sensitivity mean score (5.06 ± 0.49) compared to female students (4.87 ± 0.43), and students who reported receiving AI education (5.07 ± 0.53) had higher scores than those who did not (4.89 ± 0.43) (Table 1).

A significant difference was found in positive attitude toward AI scores based on students’ use of AI tools during their professional education ($t=2.811, p=0.006$) and their opinions on the impact of AI on nursing care ($F=4.659, p=0.004$). Students who used AI tools during their professional education

had higher positive attitude scores (3.81 ± 0.74) compared to those who did not use them (3.49 ± 0.72). Post hoc comparisons using the Tukey test indicated that students who think AI affects nursing care had significantly higher positive attitude scores toward AI ($p=0.007$) compared to those who were “Undecided.” Additionally, “Undecided” students had significantly lower scores compared to those who responded “No opinion” ($p=0.028$). A significant difference was found in negative attitude toward AI scores based on students’ AI education status ($t=-2.669, p=0.008$). Students who received AI education had lower negative attitude scores (2.51 ± 0.78) compared to those who did not (2.91 ± 0.87) (Table 1).

A significant positive correlation was found between the students' total MMSQSN score and Positive Attitude toward AI score ($r= 0.157, p=0.036$), while a significant negative correlation was found with their Negative Attitude toward AI score ($r= -0.420, p < 0.001$) (Table 3). Simple linear regression analyses were conducted to determine the effect of students' ethical sensitivity levels on their positive and negative attitudes toward AI, revealing that both models were statistically significant. The MMSQSN score significantly predicted the Positive Attitudes toward AI score ($F= 4.470, p= 0.036$), explaining 2.5% of the variance ($R^2= 0.025$). As the

MMSQSN score increased, the Negative Attitudes toward AI score significantly decreased ($F=37.752, p < 0.001$), and the model explained 17.7% of the variance ($R^2= 0.177$) (Table 4).

Table 3. Relationship Between MMSQSN and GAAIS ($n=178$)

Scales	Positive Attitudes toward AI	Negative Attitudes toward AI
MMSQSN	$r = 0.16^*, p = 0.036$	$r = -0.42^{**}, p < 0.001$

**p < 0.05; **p < 0.01; r = Pearson Correlation*

Table 4. Results of Simple Linear Regression Analyses Examining the Effect of Ethical Sensitivity on Positive and Negative Attitudes Toward Artificial Intelligence

Independent variable	Dependent variable	B	SE	β	T	p	F	Model (p)	R ²
MMSQSN	Positive Attitudes	0.252	0.119	0.157	2.114	0.036	4.47	0.036	0.025
	Negative Attitudes	-0.781	0.127	-0.420	-6.144	0.0	37.752	< 0.001	0.177

B = unstandardized coefficients; SE = standard error; β = standardized coefficients beta; F = Analysis of variance value.

DISCUSSION

This study examined the relationship between nursing students' ethical sensitivity and their attitudes toward AI. The nursing students' ethical sensitivity levels were neutral (moderate), and they generally exhibited a positive attitude toward AI. Ethical sensitivity influenced attitudes toward AI.

Ethical challenges are commonly encountered by nurses and nursing students in clinical practice. They need to have a high level of ethical sensitivity to recognize these issues². In this study, the students' mean total MMSQSN score was 148.05 ± 13.97 . The total score obtainable from the scale ranges between 30 and 210, and as the score increases, the level of ethical sensitivity also increases. Scale score averages are evaluated as 5.8-5, indicating an "important" level, and 4.9-3.1, indicating a "neutral" level. Accordingly, the mean score of 4.93 corresponds to the "neutral" level but is very close to the "important" level⁹. This suggests that students have a moderate level of ethical awareness, with a tendency to perceive ethical sensitivity as important, although they have not yet fully developed it. Similarly, a study conducted in Iran found that students' ethical sensitivity levels were at an intermediate level¹⁸. Likewise, Akça et al. (2017)⁶ determined

that nursing students had moderate levels of moral sensitivity.

In another study that used a similar scale to this study, the mean total score of the students was reported as 149.70 ± 19.84 , indicating that their ethical sensitivity was above the moderate level¹⁹. In Yang's (2024)² study, nursing students' moral sensitivity had an average score of 4.25 out of 5, indicating an ethical sensitivity level above the midpoint. In two studies using the Moral Sensitivity Questionnaire, nursing students were found to have high levels of ethical sensitivity^{7,20}. These findings indicate that the ethical sensitivity levels of nursing students generally range from moderate to high. It is thought that enhancing the ethical sensitivity of nursing students, who will become the nurses of the future, will help them recognize and find solutions to ethical problems in the healthcare environment, where such problems frequently occur. Therefore, nurse educators should develop educational strategies in the nursing curriculum aimed at increasing moral sensitivity.

In this study, male students had higher ethical sensitivity. Some studies have shown that students' gender affects their level of ethical sensitivity^{19,21}, while others have reported no significant effect of gender on ethical sensitivity^{6,20}. Similar to the present study, Serçe and Vicdan (2025)¹⁹ also found

that male students had higher levels of ethical sensitivity. In the study by Gürdoğan et al. (2018)⁷, the scores of the Orientation sub-dimension differed according to gender, with female students scoring lower than male students. On the other hand, Büyük and Ünalı (2020)²¹ reported that female students demonstrated higher ethical sensitivity than their male counterparts. This difference between studies may be due to differences in variables such as the scales used, sample characteristics, cultural characteristics, and the scope of ethics education. These differences may have led to different evaluations of students' ethical sensitivity levels.

In this study, students who received education related to AI demonstrated higher levels of ethical sensitivity. This may be attributed to these students have greater exposure to the relationship between AI technologies and ethics, providing them with opportunities to question ethical dilemmas. A systematic review and meta-analysis emphasized the necessity of including AI-related education in the student curriculum¹. Our study findings indicate that such education could help enhance ethical sensitivity.

The students' mean positive attitude score on the GAAIS was 44.08 ± 8.96 , while the mean negative attitude score was 22.52 ± 6.92 . Considering the minimum and maximum possible scores for each subscale, it can be said that students have high levels of positive attitudes and moderate levels of negative attitudes. This finding suggests that students recognize the potential benefits of AI but still have some reservations. The literature also indicates that while there is a generally positive perspective toward AI, there are concerns related to ethical issues^{2,3}. It is thought that students' moderate levels of negative attitudes may be related to these concerns. Nevertheless, it can be said that nursing students generally have a positive attitude toward AI technology. The findings of previous studies on nursing students' attitudes toward AI are consistent with the results of this study. In the study conducted by Kandemir and Azizoğlu (2024)²², the mean score for the Positive Attitude subscale of nurses working in a university hospital was 43.74 ± 6.87 , while the mean score for the Negative Attitude subscale was 25.53 ± 5.64 . In Muradı's (2025)²³ study, nursing students' mean scores for the Positive Attitude and Negative Attitude subscales were 42.99 ± 6.54 and 22.54 ± 5.26 , respectively. In the study by Elmaoğlu and Güleç (2015)²⁴, the mean Positive Attitude subscale score of nursing students was 42.86 ± 7.69 , and the mean Negative Attitude

subdimension score was 22.13 ± 5.34 . In another study conducted with nursing and midwifery students, the mean scores of the students' Positive and Negative Attitude sub-dimensions were found to be 42.67 ± 7.10 and 24.08 ± 5.81 , respectively²⁵. These findings are similar to our study findings and show that nursing students generally have a positive attitude towards AI. Students' positive attitudes towards AI facilitate their acceptance, adoption, and implementation of AI technology^{1,26} and their behavioral intentions to use AI-based health technologies^{4,11}. Since nursing students' attitudes towards AI are positively correlated with their readiness for AI²⁴, improving these attitudes is also important for students' readiness levels. In this context, it is believed that nursing students' positive attitudes towards AI will enhance their readiness to use AI, support their adoption, acceptance, and effective use of AI technologies in their educational processes and future professional lives. Indeed, the use of AI in nursing is expected to increase.

In this study, the majority of students use AI both in their daily lives and educational processes, and students who use AI for educational purposes have higher positive attitudes towards AI. This may be related to the fact that students who use AI tools have the opportunity to experience the potential benefits of AI. Students' use of AI technology may have contributed to their better understanding of this technology and their feeling more competent.

In this study, students who believed that AI had an impact on nursing care demonstrated a higher level of positive attitude toward AI compared to those who were undecided. This finding suggests that students' perceptions of the role of AI in nursing care may influence their attitudes toward AI. Accordingly, it is believed that educational programs that raise awareness and provide concrete examples of how AI can contribute to nursing care may support the development of more positive attitudes among students.

In the current study, nursing students who received AI education demonstrated lower negative attitude scores compared to those who did not. Similarly, Yang's (2024)² study revealed that experience in AI-related education had a significant impact on AI ethics awareness. Students who had received AI education were more likely to exhibit higher levels of ethical awareness regarding AI. In the study by Abuadas and Albikawi (2025)⁴, nursing students' engagement

in AI workshops or training was found to be significantly associated with greater moral sensitivity and more positive attitudes toward AI. These findings suggest that educational programs play an important role in reducing negative attitudes toward AI. In this context, nursing educators should prioritize AI education in their curricula, and healthcare policymakers should invest in educational resources. By doing so, they will contribute to the preparation of nurses who are both equipped to provide AI-supported care and more positively inclined toward this technology.

The inevitability of ethical issues in the use of AI highlights the necessity of a high level of ethical awareness to prevent such problems². Despite the optimistic perspective on the use of AI in healthcare, ethical issues remain a concern³. These concerns may influence individuals' attitudes toward AI. In this study, the ethical sensitivity levels of nursing students had a predictive effect on their positive and negative attitudes towards AI. Similarly, in the study by Abuadas and Albikawi (2025)⁴, positive attitudes were reported to be positively associated with AI ethical awareness. Moreover, moral sensitivity was identified as the key influencing factor in this awareness. This finding suggests that ethical sensitivity may play a guiding role in nursing students' attitudes toward AI. Students with high ethical sensitivity may have been more positive about this technology if they realized the contributions that AI could provide to nursing care. This may have allowed these students to develop a positive attitude by analyzing the potential benefits of AI more consciously, as well as realizing its potential harms.

Limitations

Conducting the study at a single university may limit the generalizability of the findings. The low predictive power of the model can be considered a limitation of the study. Furthermore, not conducting an analysis based on the sub-dimensions of the MMSQSN may have limited the possibility of a more detailed evaluation of the findings.

CONCLUSION

The nursing students' ethical sensitivity levels were neutral (moderate), while they generally exhibited a positive attitude toward AI. While students' ethical sensitivity was found to be associated with receiving education on AI and gender, their

attitudes toward AI were associated with receiving education on AI, using AI tools, and their views on AI's impact on nursing care. As students' ethical sensitivities increased, their positive attitudes towards AI increased, and their negative attitudes decreased. Ethical sensitivity was a predictor of attitudes toward AI. Enhancing students' ethical sensitivity may contribute to fostering more positive attitudes toward AI.

To foster nursing students' positive attitudes toward AI, it is recommended to integrate AI into the curriculum as either mandatory or elective courses and provide training on AI. The content of this education should include fundamental concepts of AI technologies, areas of application in nursing practice, integration into decision support systems, and its role in patient care processes. In addition, ethical aspects such as data privacy, patient confidentiality, and professional responsibility should be addressed in a comprehensive manner. Providing students with opportunities to experience AI applications and emphasizing the contributions of AI to nursing care may play a significant role in shaping their attitudes. Nursing educators need to guide students in this process, enhance their ethical awareness, and serve as role models. Being role models in ethical decision-making and AI-related ethical sensitivity by nurse educators and clinical nurses can contribute to the development of students' ethical awareness and sensitivity, thus supporting their readiness and attitudes toward AI technology. Additionally, it is recommended that further studies be conducted with larger sample sizes to investigate various factors influencing attitudes toward AI.

Conflict of interest

The authors report no conflict of interest.

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No

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